

ROLE OF YOGA IN MINIMIZING STRESS MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Form the medieval periods onwards, Yoga is a most common exercise in Indian heritage. In our holy book 'Geeta', Yoga was already introduced. We all know that our body and mind are always connected with each other. If our mind is calm, then our muscular strength in our body will also calm. Now-a-days it is common that our daily work pressure and various demands in our life create a stress; which will seriously affect our physical and mental health. Stress can lead to a many high factors of illness. Therefore, it is very much important to do Yoga each and every day, as it helps each person's for reducing stress. Generally, stress may be internal or external; that's why people can feel uneasy in any place. Yoga helps a person's in controlling internal stress. We all know that Yoga means some kind of physical sitting and some breathing methods; as it helps to expand the strength of the body, good oxygen level and good function of a hormone in our body. It is completely qualitative type work and all details was gathered from secondary sources i.e website, articles and journals. This work mainly focuses on various kind of stress, stress and its indication, role of Yoga and connection among various styles in reducing stress and some findings and suggestions.

Keywords: Yoga, Stress, physical health and mental health

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Introduction

Stress can harm physical and mental health of our body. Most of the people having stress in their life. Stress can harm the mind and behavior in different ways. It negatively effects the health conditions. The most important tool for maintaining a stress is Yoga. When people feel lots of stress our nervous system discharge lots of stress hormone. Some physical effect in our body such as heartbeat runs faster, excess hair fall, body weight may loss or may gain, pressure may be high and digestive problems etc. Some emotional effect such as anxiety, depression, intake lots of alcohol etc. We generally know that stress is most harmful thing in human's life; but if we have little bit of stress that helps us to do any kind of work under some pressure and motivate or inspire to do more better (Behere et al., 2011). That's why it is very much essential to do yoga in daily life as it helps each person to think and live in a good way and it brings peace in the society also.

Review of Literature

Some review of literature ae as follows –

1) Catherin Woodyard (2011) told in her study that yoga not only escalate

with Indian countries; it also scatters in western countries. They think that yoga is one of the essential works in their everyday life. Anxiety, depression and stress can be minimized by doing yoga and it may also reduce different kinds of sickness.

2) Manoj Sharma (2013) told in his study that stress can seriously affects the health of a human. There is favourable relationship between physical and mental results in relation with stress. So, yoga is the only powerful weapon for stress management.

3) Manish Dwivedi (2014) told in his study that stress is one of the problems is that creates a various kind of sickness. Excessive stress can enhance high pressure, anxiety, heart attack and depression. Yoga can maintain steadiness between body and mind. Yoga keeps our body physically, mentally and emotionally stable.

4) Kristen E. Riley and Park (2014) found that there is a good relationship between stress and yoga. Through Yoga stress will be minimized.

5) Sunil Kumar Yadav (2014) told in his study that stress can be managed by doing yoga. There are different kinds of postures in Yoga that can help to minimize

stress. Doing meditation is also very useful for reducing a stress.

6) Josefien J.F. Breedvelt (2019) found that if one can do yoga and meditation simultaneously then it gives a better outcome. Yoga works like a medicine for maintaining a stress and it does not have any kind of side effects and it gives a person's a lot of peace.

7) Neeru Devi and Sheetal (2020) told in their study that sometimes positive stress helps to defeat with different kinds of hurdle, whereas negative stress effects physical and mental health of a person's. Yoga also helps all people who are in workplace for controlling stress- and stress-free people can work actively and they can internally motivated.

8) Pooja Swami Sahni (2021) found that at the time of covid 19 many youths feel stress and for that situation doing a yoga helps to reduce stress. Many adults lost their job and having lots of dilemmas. So, at that time yoga become a most powerful therapy.

Research Gap

I have done some review that mainly focuses on importance of yoga and how it helps to maintain a physical health of a

person. But form my point of view, yoga is not only embedded with physical health but it also helps an individual for overall development.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Some objectives are as follows:

- a) To know the effects of stress on an individual.
- b) To understand that yoga will help an individual in overall development.
- c) To know the connection between various yoga postures and stress control.

Research Methodology

This is a descriptive study, it describes all facts. The overall information was collected from only secondary sources such as research paper and articles. The main focus of this study is how yoga is essential in controlling a stress.

Stress, Its Types and Some Symptoms

In a simple way we can say that stress is a kind of pressure that makes a people to feel anxiety and unhappy. Stress not only hamper the health but it also inspires or motivates an individual. Long

term stress can affect the persons mentally. At that time persons will not behave properly. Extreme stress makes an individual physically weak. He/she cannot able to do any kind of work competently. Stress is affected by the outside elements of environment. Stress is not always a negative issue.

Types of Stress

There are different kinds of stress, but mainly we have discussed 3 kinds of stress are as follows: –

1) Acute Stress – Acute stress is a very normal type of stress and it is common in our everyday life. It is very short – term stress.

2) Episodic Acute Stress – It is common stress and frequently occurrence stress.

3) Chronic Stress – It is a long-term stress. It is dangerous and high level.

Some Symptoms of Stress

Cognitive Symptoms

- Recalling problems
- Does not able to concentrate properly
 - Does not able to judge what is wrong or right.

- Concrete only on negative things.
- Feeling too much anxious.
- Always worrying in all things.

Emotional Symptoms

- Impulsive
- Irritable
- Feeling overjoy
- Feeling unhappiness
- Feeling depression

Physical Symptoms

- Feeling unsteadiness
- Fast heartbeat
- Problem in digestive system
- Gastro problem
- Heart attack
- Behavioural Symptoms
- Isolated from others
- Frustration
- Drug addicted
- Rapidness
- Not willingness to do any work

Relationship Between Yoga Styles and Stress Management

1) Sukhasana – This kind of postures will make mind at a peace and all kinds of anxiety is totally removed from our body.

2) Marjariasana (Cat pose) –
By doing this postures our mind will be free
from any kind of stress and our body will be
calm.

3) Salamba Sirsasana
(headstand) – By doing this kind postures
the flow of blood will reversed and we will
get relieve from stress.

4) Uttana Shishosana
(Extended puppy pose) – By doing this our
body get control from stress.

5) Anjali Mudra (Salutation
Seal) – By doing this, our mind gets calm
and peace.

6) Paschimottanasana (Seated
forward bend pose) – After doing this
asana, stress from our body is totally
removed and we can do any kind of work
more efficiently.

7) Janu Sirsasana (Forward
Bend) – By doing this, it also relief our
body from stress.

8) Balasana (child pose) -By
doing this, it gives comfort to our body and
it keeps our body stress free.

9) Svasana (corpse pose) – By
doing this our body become calm and it
gives long term peace.

Meditation and Stress Management

Doing Meditation is a very essential
in everyday life and it helps to concentrate
our mind. Meditation can transform or
change the life of an individual and a person
can enter to a inner world and feel a peace.
By doing continues Meditation one can able
to overcome new issues and achieve new
things and get motivated to do any kind of
work. One can focus in one direction. So,
meditation is one kind of permanent
solution in controlling stress also.

Pranayama and Stress Management

Pranayama is a combination of two
words. First is 'PRANA' which means
energy and second is 'AYAM' which
means control. It means it controls our body
energy. Pranayama controls our flow of
oxygen in our brain and blood. It also
controls the flow of blood in our body. It
can control our mind and body also. Asana
will give concentration to a soul and it
controls our thoughts, emotions and reduce
excessive stress. It helps our body to calm,
control our hypertension along with peace
in mind and also relax our nervous system.

Some physiological well-being after doing yoga

- Gives a good health
- Makes a balance of a body weight
- Gives much muscle mobility and strength
- Having proper blood circulation and healthy digestive system
- Enhance sleep
- Reduce our daily tension
- Enhance our body posture

Some psychological well-being after doing yoga

- Reduce our stress, anxiety and depression
- It can enhance our thinking power, attention power, memory and concentration power
- It helps our body and mind calm
- Enhance our mood
- Think about our self-awareness
- Enhance our mind and body balance

Some Ways for Stress Management

- Recognize warning signs –If we are able to recognize the early signs of a stress; then it is much useful to us to

know when we are feeling stressed. Feeling stress is totally different from one individual to another individual. Some having Headaches, hot tempered, frequently feeling irritable.

- Recognize triggers –We know that some kinds of particular triggers can maximize our stress level and it is very hard to manage it. But if we able to understand what kinds of triggers will come then we can manage our stress level. Example of triggers may be late night party, seeing an ideal person only etc.
- Proper Routines - In our day-to-day life; maintaining a proper routine can makes a person stress free and help us to reduce stress. We have to do exercise every day, maintain a proper food times, do some walking and go to bed in proper time and plan what kind of jobs be done in each day.
- Spend time with people who care about us – Always spend time with that people who care about us. Like family members and friends who can help you and can uplift us in our difficult situation. It is very much helpful when we tell or share our personal feeling and thoughts with others person then we can reduce our stress in day-to-day life.

- Having good health – Everyday, we have to take a healthy food habit, doing regular exercise and having a proper sleep. If we found that our mind is not calm then we can do anything like dancing, talking with other, walking and listening music. We have to avoid of taking any kind of drug and alcohol.
- Doing relaxation –If we take load or pressure of doing any job then it creates a stress. So doing relaxation is very much important as it helps our whole body and nervous system to relax. We have to practice yoga and mediation and do any kind of relaxing work or activities, listening music, reading story books and gardening etc.
- Doing Yoga – For reducing stress, we have to do various kinds of asana of yoga in regular basis. That makes our body and mind in a peaceful stage.
- The first cause is organizational cause. Many people’s jobs are insecurity, as this creates stress.
- Many individuals did their job work in a very difficult and uncomfortable place. Room temperatures are very high or low, very crowding place, no low voice, poor lighting and unproper machinery all those creates a stress.
- If any person does not get social supports, then that persons feels isolated from a society that cause a stress.
- If people work for long times or hours a day and have a heavy workload as it creates stress.
- Job must be in their own choice otherwise they feel bored.
- There must be no discrimination among colleagues.

Occupational Stress

Occupational stress is a kind of stress that derived from work pressure. Work pressure is generally created when one’s knowledge and abilities does not match with their work and not able to cope up with.

Some causes of occupational stress

Findings And Suggestions

Some findings and suggestions are as follows:

- 1) Mainly doing yoga increase physical health in human but if anyone can do in regular basis it will free from mental stress also.

2) Anyone can do some type of asana in workplace also that will help free from stress and can do any work efficiently.

3) After doing yoga our body will be free from stress and it enhance the mental state of a person.

4) By doing yoga, a person can develop whole personality, it connects spirituality with an individual and plays a vital role in society.

5) After doing yoga, if stress is decreased a person will be motivated to do any kind of work.

6) Yoga is one of the best treatments in a very natural way.

Conclusion

So, from the above we may conclude that after doing various postures a person can be free from stress and will physically, mentally and spiritually good in all situations. We can say that in corporate world, yoga and meditation plays a vital role, as it keeps all employees to be happy at workplace and always be motivated. They are internally and externally healthy. Yoga always creates a connection between body and mind. If a person not physically and psychologically well, then he/she goes

in a deep worry. At last, we can say that yoga is a best tool for reducing stress.

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